

[Video marketing](#) is a type of content marketing, an internet marketing technique in which individuals or businesses create short videos to promote their brands, products, services, or other specific topics. It can convey messages faster and more efficiently than any different kind of content.

Quick Video Marketing Stats

- 64% of marketers say video will take the upper half of their strategies very soon, according to Nielsen.
- 69% is the amount of consumer internet traffic that video content will account for in the near future, told Cisco.
- 70% of marketers interviewed for a Vidyard's report say that video gets them higher conversions than any other type of content.
- 73% of U.S. adults are more likely to purchase a product or service after watching an online video explaining it.
- Videos attract 300% more traffic than any other kind of content.
- Two times more in only four years in US [digital video](#) ad spending is the prediction an eMarketer research made.

Video Marketing Benefits

- It helps to build your brand, beginning with increasing the brand's trust and awareness.
- It helps in engaging prospective customers. The people will know you better and feel more inclined to buy from you.
- It helps to improve your site, reducing bounce rates, more time on site, Google ranks pages with videos higher.
- It develops your email marketing campaigns. Link to or embed a video in an email to increase your open and click-through rates and reduce your unsubscribe rates.

- It will help you improve your conversions, leads.

Video Creation Issue

Have you ever wanted to create a sale video, but the technical issues have always prevented you from getting started?

Believe me, I know what it's like.

There's nothing more disappointing than having spent hours trying to use video software editor, only to then failure of making a sale video.

To avoid being left behind, you need someone who can explain how the technology works step-by-step, in simple words, without all the complicated jargon.

That's why today, I'm delighted to share with you my latest product - [Vidnami](#).

What Is Vidnami?

[Vidnami](#) is an online video creator software that allows you to produce fast, easy, and professional-looking videos within short minutes.

You can use it to create a quick video for social media sites, blog posts, influencer videos, instant ads, sales videos, online courses, property listing.

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